

An analytical method for solving the model of pollution for a system of lakes

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ABSTRACT

Pollution has become a very serious threat to our environment. Monitoring pollution is the first step toward planning to save the environment. The use of differential equations, monitoring pollution has become possible. In this paper, Laplace transform method is introduced to solve modelling the pollution of a system of lakes by a system of differential equations.

We convert the proposed a system of ordinary differential equation (ODE) using a Laplace transform (LT). Solving this system and applying inverse LT an exact solution of the problem is obtained. It is observed that the LT is a simple and reliable technique for solving such equations.

A numerical example is presented to show the performance and accuracy of the proposed method.

KEYWORDS: modeling the pollution of a system of lakes, Laplace transform, system of ordinary differential equation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of 1994, Taylor, Chebyshev and Legendre (matrix and collocation) methods have been used by Sezer et al. [1-3] To solve differential, Fredholm-Volterra integral, Fredholm- Volterra integro-differential difference equations, and systems of linear differential and Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations. Also, the Bessel matrix method has been used to find the approximate solutions of differential, integral and integro-differential equations [4].

Fig. 1 shows the system of three lakes that are modeled in this study. Each lake is considered to be a large compartment and the interconnecting channels as pipes between the compartments. The direction of flow in the channels or pipes is indicated by the arrows in the figure. A pollutant is introduced into the first lake and $p(t)$ denotes the rate at which the pollutant enters the lake per unit time. The function $p(t)$ may be constant or may vary with time. We are interested in knowing the level of pollution in each lake at any time. Let $x_i(t)$ denotes the amount of pollution in lake i at any time $t \geq 0$ where $i = 1, 2, 3$. We assume the pollutant in each lake to be uniformly distributed throughout the lake by some mixing process, and the volume of water V_i in lake i remains constant for each of the lakes. Also we assume that the type of pollution is persistent and not degrading to other forms. Then the concentration of the pollutant in lake i at any time is given by

$$c_i(t) = \frac{x_i(t)}{V_i}.$$

Each lake, initially, is assumed to be free of any contaminant, so $x_i(0) = \lambda_i$ (λ_i : appropriate constants) for each $i = 1, 2, 3$. To model the dynamic behavior of the system of lakes, we let constant F_{ji} the flow rate from lake i to lake j . The flux of pollutant flowing from lake i into lake j at any time t , denoted by $r_{ij}(t)$, is defined by

$$r_{ji} = F_{ji}c_i(t) = F_{ji} \frac{x_i(t)}{V_i}.$$

Thus $r_{ij}(t)$ measures the rate at which the concentration of pollutant in lake i flows into lake j at time t . We will observe that

Rate of change of pollutant = Input rate - output rate.

Figure1. system of three lakes with interconnecting channels.

Applying this principle to each lake results in the following system of first order equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx_1}{dt} = \frac{F_{13}}{V_3} x_3(t) + p(t) - \frac{F_{31}}{V_1} x_1(t) - \frac{F_{21}}{V_1} x_1(t) \\ \frac{dx_2}{dt} = \frac{F_{21}}{V_1} x_1(t) - \frac{F_{32}}{V_2} x_2(t) \\ \frac{dx_3}{dt} = \frac{F_{31}}{V_1} x_1(t) + \frac{F_{32}}{V_2} x_2(t) - \frac{F_{13}}{V_3} x_3(t), \end{cases} \quad 0 \leq t \leq b \quad (1)$$

with the initial conditions

$$x_i(0) = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

For the volume of each lake to remain constant, the flow rate into each lake must balance the flow out of the lake. So we obtain the following conditions:

$$\text{Lake 1: } F_{13} = F_{21} + F_{31},$$

$$\text{Lake 2: } F_{21} = F_{32},$$

Lake 3: $F_{31} + F_{32} = F_{13}$.

Here, $x_1(t)$, $x_2(t)$, $x_3(t)$ are the unknown functions, the known function $p(t)$ is defined on interval $0 \leq t \leq b$ and also F_{31} , F_{13} , F_{32} , F_{21} , V_1 , V_2 and V_3 are appropriate constants.

Definition 1. [5] The Laplace transform of a function $f(t)$, $t > 0$ is defined by

$$\mathcal{L}[f(t)] = \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-st} f(t) dt,$$

Where s can be either real or complex.

Theorem 1. [6] The Laplace transform $\mathcal{L}[f(t)]$ of the derivative is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}[f^{(n)}(t)] = s^n F(s) - s^{n-1} f(0) - s^{n-2} f'(0) - \dots - f^{(n-1)}(0). \quad (2)$$

2 THE METHOD FOR SOLUTION OF A SYSTEM OF DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

Firstly, we consider the differential equation. We apply Laplace transform first on both sides of (1)

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{L}\left[\frac{dx_1}{dt}\right] = \frac{F_{13}}{V_3} \mathcal{L}[x_3(t)] + \mathcal{L}[p(t)] - \frac{F_{31}}{V_1} \mathcal{L}[x_1(t)] - \frac{F_{21}}{V_1} \mathcal{L}[x_1(t)] \\ \mathcal{L}\left[\frac{dx_2}{dt}\right] = \frac{F_{21}}{V_1} \mathcal{L}[x_1(t)] - \frac{F_{32}}{V_2} \mathcal{L}[x_2(t)] \\ \mathcal{L}\left[\frac{dx_3}{dt}\right] = \frac{F_{31}}{V_1} \mathcal{L}[x_1(t)] + \frac{F_{32}}{V_2} \mathcal{L}[x_2(t)] - \frac{F_{13}}{V_3} \mathcal{L}[x_3(t)], \end{cases} \quad 0 \leq t \leq b \quad (3)$$

Using the differentiation property of Laplace transform (2) we get

$$\begin{cases} s \mathcal{L}[x_1(t)] - x_1(0) = \frac{F_{13}}{V_3} \mathcal{L}[x_3(t)] + \mathcal{L}[p(t)] - \frac{F_{31}}{V_1} \mathcal{L}[x_1(t)] - \frac{F_{21}}{V_1} \mathcal{L}[x_1(t)] \\ s \mathcal{L}[x_2(t)] - x_2(0) = \frac{F_{21}}{V_1} \mathcal{L}[x_1(t)] - \frac{F_{32}}{V_2} \mathcal{L}[x_2(t)] \\ s \mathcal{L}[x_3(t)] - x_3(0) = \frac{F_{31}}{V_1} \mathcal{L}[x_1(t)] + \frac{F_{32}}{V_2} \mathcal{L}[x_2(t)] - \frac{F_{13}}{V_3} \mathcal{L}[x_3(t)], \end{cases} \quad 0 \leq t \leq b$$

By solving the above equation system and applying inverse Laplace transform to (3), we can obtain the unknown functions $x_i(t)$, $i = 1, 2, 3$.

3 ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

In this section we will apply the LT described in the previous sections to find exact solutions for three pollution.

3.1 Example 1 [7]

Consider the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx_1}{dt} = \frac{38}{1180} x_3(t) + \{1 + \sin(t)\} - \frac{20}{2900} x_1(t) - \frac{18}{2900} x_1(t) \\ \frac{dx_2}{dt} = \frac{18}{2900} x_1(t) - \frac{18}{850} x_2(t) \\ \frac{dx_3}{dt} = \frac{20}{2900} x_1(t) + \frac{18}{850} (t) - \frac{38}{1180} x_3(t), \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

with the initial conditions:

$$x_i(0) = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

Also, this example $p(t) = 1 + \sin(t)$ and the parameter values have been fixed to $V_1 = 2900 \text{ mi}^3$, $V_2 = 850 \text{ mi}^3$, $V_3 = 1180 \text{ mi}^3$, $F_{21} = 18 \frac{\text{mi}^3}{\text{year}}$, $F_{32} = 18 \frac{\text{mi}^3}{\text{year}}$.

We solve the system of equations (4) by the LT method. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}[x_1(t)] &= \frac{17110(1 + s + s^2)}{s(-433 + 17110s - 433s^2 + 17110s^3)}, \\ \mathcal{L}[x_2(t)] &= \frac{45135(1 + s + s^2)}{s(9 + 425s)(-433 + 17110s - 433s^2 + 17110s^3)}, \\ \mathcal{L}[x_3(t)] &= \frac{59(171 + 4250s)(1 + s + s^2)}{5s^2(9 + 425s)(-433 + 17110s - 433s^2 + 17110s^3)}, \end{aligned}$$

and by applying inverse Laplace transform

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= 1.348913326540651 \\ &\quad \times 10^{-7} (-2.92939589 \times 10^8 + 3.00348219 \\ &\quad \times 10^8 2.718281828459045^{0.025306838106370542t} - 7408630.0 \cos(t) \\ &\quad - 187489. \sin(t)), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} x_2 &= 45135. \left(-0.00025660764690787786 \right. \\ &\quad + 0.000136747394240249382.718281828459045^{-0.021176470588235293t} \\ &\quad + 0.00011985968528374482.718281828459045^{0.025306838106370542t} \\ &\quad \left. + 1.88907569058526 \times 10^{-14} (30035. \cos(t) - 7275647.0 \sin(t)) \right), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} x_3 &= 11.8 \left(-0.7962707145485869 \right. \\ &\quad - 0.52305878296895392.718281828459045^{-0.021176470588235293t} \\ &\quad + 1.31930358347215852.718281828459045^{0.025306838106370542t} \\ &\quad - 0.04387990762124711t + 1.88907569058526 \\ &\quad \left. \times 10^{-14} (1.371784387 \times 10^9 \cos(t) - 3.0916363765 \times 10^{10} \sin(t)) \right). \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Example 2 (Linear Input Model) [8]

This input model is used when the pollutant is introduced into the first lake with a linear concentration; that is $p(t) = ct$, where c is a positive constant. If we take $c = 100$ then system (1) becomes

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx_1}{dt} = \frac{38}{1180} x_3(t) + 100t - \frac{20}{2900} x_1(t) - \frac{18}{2900} x_1(t) \\ \frac{dx_2}{dt} = \frac{18}{2900} x_1(t) - \frac{18}{850} x_2(t) \\ \frac{dx_3}{dt} = \frac{20}{2900} x_1(t) + \frac{18}{850} (t) - \frac{38}{1180} x_3(t), \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

with the initial conditions:

$$x_i(0) = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

Applying present method, we have

$$x_1 = 9.125868717631434(-17110. + 17110.2.718281828459045^{0.025306838106370542t} - 433.t),$$

$$x_2 = 4513500.0(0.0019777291955037496 - 0.006597157734434682.718281828459045^{-0.021176470588235293t} + 0.004619428538930932.718281828459045^{0.025306838106370542t} - 0.00025660764690787786t),$$

$$x_3 = 1180.(-76.08048764658481 + 25.234128334212652.718281828459045^{-0.021176470588235293t} + 50.846359312372172.718281828459045^{0.025306838106370542t} - 0.7523908069273397t - 0.021939953810623556t^2).$$

3.3 Example 3 (Exponentially Decaying Input Model) [8]

In this example, we assume the pollutant input to have the form $p(t) = ae^{-bt}$. This corresponds to a heavy dumping of the pollutant. If we take $a = 200, b = 10$, then system (1) becomes

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx_1}{dt} = \frac{38}{1180} x_3(t) + 200e^{-10t} - \frac{20}{2900} x_1(t) - \frac{18}{2900} x_1(t) \\ \frac{dx_2}{dt} = \frac{18}{2900} x_1(t) - \frac{18}{850} x_2(t) \\ \frac{dx_3}{dt} = \frac{20}{2900} x_1(t) + \frac{18}{850} (t) - \frac{38}{1180} x_3(t), \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

with the initial conditions:

$$x_i(0) = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

Applying present method, we have

$$x_1 = 19.9495140876682632.718281828459045^{-10.t} \\ (-1.+2.718281828459045^{10.02530683810637t}),$$

$$x_2 = 9027000.0(1.374624386807381 \times 10^{-9} 2.718281828459045^{-10.t} \\ - 2.964726834621185 \times 10^{-7} 2.718281828459045^{-0.021176470588235293t} \\ + 2.950980590753111 \times 10^{-7} 2.718281828459045^{0.025306838106370542t}),$$

$$x_3 = 2360. (-0.004387990762124711 \\ + 0.0000058186475669169662.718281828459045^{-10.t} \\ + 0.00113400801424260362.718281828459045^{-0.021176470588235293t} \\ + 0.00324816410031519062.718281828459045^{0.025306838106370542t}).$$

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we present a new technique by using the Laplace transform to solve the problem of pollutions of three lakes with interconnecting channels. This method is easily implemented and it is simple and calculates the exact solution of system (1). In total, the presented method is easy and rapid to compute.

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